

An Emergence of a Planning Support System for Collaborative Urban Planning Through a User-Centred Design Approach: The Case of “Virtual Green Planner”

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Abstract

In contrast to traditional public participation methods in planning, digital tools need to be developed by information technology experts which means the public cannot customise their approaches to participation without IT expertise. This study examines the effectiveness of a user-centred design approach in developing a planning support system for collaborative urban planning. The findings show that tool developers play a crucial role in shaping the tool, while users could provide inputs through user research conducted by the researchers. A systemic challenge between tool developers, users, researchers, and funders is revealed.

Keywords

user-centred design (UCD),
planning support system (PSS),
collaborative urban planning,
user research

Introduction

As the information society has flourished, it has brought forth new realms of public engagement in planning practices. The multitude and increasing diversity of participants have unveiled a wide range of knowledge associated with planning matters. Meanwhile, digitalisation has brought about noteworthy effects on participation and communication methods, enabling more effective integration of diverse voices from a pluralistic society into present-day planning practices (Staffans et al., 2020). Among various types of digital instruments, planning support systems (PSS) have been proven to be valuable for planning (Pelzer et al., 2014). PSS can be defined as ‘geo-information based tools intended to support planners in planning tasks such as information handling, communication and analysis in planning processes’ (Vonk & Geertman, 2008). In recent decades, the supportive role of PSS has been expanded to public engagement (Kahila & Kytä, 2009) as the ‘collaborative turn’ (Healey, 2003) in planning emphasises social interaction and participation. A growing body of literature has been focused on the usefulness of PSS that supports individuals’ participation

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(e.g., Kahila-Tani et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2019). However, little attention has been paid to the development process of PSS.

A dilemma between the diverse demands of participants and the need for simplistic PSS was identified from previous research. On the one hand, one of the challenges of public engagement in planning is the ability to reach a broad spectrum of people (Kahila-Tani et al., 2019). Research suggests that digital tools can attract a different group of participants than traditional tools (McLain et al., 2017). This implies that digital tools should not be substitutes for analogue participation tools. Instead, they should be regarded as complementary tools that offer faster and more efficient ways of establishing communication channels between different actors (Kahila-Tani et al., 2019). When more diverse groups are reached, demands for collaborative tools become more varied (Nummi et al., 2022), for example, in terms of the participants' skills and resources available, such as the availability of digital tools and timing of participation (Aguilar, 2022), or in terms of the participants' cultural backgrounds (Harsia & Nummi, 2024). Moreover, planners and participants have different expectations of participation tools (Aguilar, 2022; Nummi et al., 2022). In the meantime, previous research has pointed out the dichotomy between the need for simplistic tools and complex planning tasks (Vonk & Geertman, 2008). Following Vonk and Geertman's conclusion, we argue that the complexity of planning issues should be addressed by dedicated tools that support breaking the planning task down into smaller ones and solving them individually. However, an overly specialised tool would fall short of meeting the diverse needs of users (Nummi et al., 2022). For instance, a tool focused solely on zoning would not meet the expectations of those looking for a tool for the detailed design of an urban environment. Balancing the tasks of serving diverse groups and being dedicated and simplistic gives challenges to developing PSS for collaborative urban planning (CUP), in addition to the challenges of usual software development.

Agile methodologies have been commonly practised in usual software development since the Agile Manifesto (Agile Alliance, 2001) was announced. They aim to attain greater speed and flexibility in the software development process. Digital tool developers usually possess a high level of information technology (IT) expertise but are often criticised as lacking familiarity with the application domain, making them less representative of the target users (Nielsen, 2008). Vonk and Geertman (2008) suggested that a technocentric tool development approach must be avoided for developing PSS, and tool developers should focus on the demand side.

Since the 1980s, user-centred design (UCD) approaches have connected IT experts and users in human-computer interaction. Kenneth D. Eason (1995), in the ergonomics domain, pointed out two paradigms of UCD: 'design for users' and 'design by users'. He proposed a simplified classification for the paradigm selection: When the cases are psycho-social in character and require debate of value and aspirations, 'design by users' is the desirable

approach; when a generic product is being built without specific users in mind, the approach taken is 'design for users'. When there is a mixture of both methods, a mixed strategy called 'design for users with users' should be applied. Such strategy implies participatory or co-design approaches where the user plays an active role in the tool development process (Kaulio, 1998; Sanders & Stappers, 2008). A PSS for CUP (PSSfCUP) faces local knowledge and bespoke planning practices (Geertman & Stillwell, 2012), as well as value debate and generic demands as it supports the general public in expressing their opinions (Kahila-Tani, 2015). Following Eason's categorisation, such systems require user involvement, including objective user research (UR) and collaborative design with users.

UCD methodologies, including collaborative design and UR, have been applied to achieve useful PSS (Aguilar, 2022; Brömmelstroet & Schrijnen, 2010). Usefulness refers to the tools' *usability* (i.e., how efficiently the user can accomplish the desired goal with the tool) and *utility* (i.e., how well the tool's functionalities match the task at hand) (Nielsen, 1993; Zhang et al., 2019). However, UCD methodologies have been criticised for being too research-oriented and emphasising too much usability to fit Agile software development (Larusdottir et al., 2017). Previous research pointed out the challenges of integrating UCD and Agile methodologies. Firstly, Agile software development emphasises testing functioning software and prioritises communication within the development team, while UCD methodologies emphasise communication with users and making the software usable (Al-Razgan et al., 2022; Butt et al., 2014; Larusdottir et al., 2017; Singh, 2008). User experience (UX) designers and software developers may have different attitudes towards UR. It is hard to build a common ground between UX professionals and Agile developers (Ananjeva et al., 2020; Garcia et al., 2019). The value and cultural differences can hinder collaboration between two groups of professionals. Secondly, Agile methodologies demand quick development and testing, but usability tests are time-consuming and not frequently conducted. UCD methodologies spend much time studying users before development due to the open-ended nature of design tasks (Al-Razgan et al., 2022). Occasionally, UCD prioritises measuring usability and refining design, leaving work tasks and underlying structures untouched (Larusdottir et al., 2017). The challenge is that when the deadline gets tight, usability would be cut off by Agile developers (Gulliksen et al., 2003). Thirdly, the user needs may not be identified or understood when the focus is on the customers instead of the users, as customers do not represent the users and do not necessarily have insight into the user needs. Although Agile methodologies are user- and customer-focused like UCD approaches (Silva da Silva et al., 2011), they do not clearly distinguish between customers and users (Martin et al., 2004), and have not paid much attention to usability (Gulliksen et al., 2003). It is often one person, such as a domain expert or a product manager from the client organisation, to fill both the customer and user roles during Agile development (Martin et al., 2004). It has been observed that customers do not prioritise usability when there is no economic incentive (Rosenbaum et al., 2000). On the

other hand, UCD methodologies emphasise the direct and active involvement of end-users (Gould & Lewis, 1985). Fourthly, it is often unclear who is responsible for the interaction between the development team and the users (Larusdottir et al., 2017). Gulliksen et al. (2003) described this as a 'sidecar problem' in which if someone is appointed to be responsible for usability, others will resign from their part of the responsibility.

Despite sufficient studies on integrating Agile and UCD approaches in usual software development, the performance of UCD methodologies in PSSfCUP development remains unexamined. Besides the general challenges in usual software development, we assume there will be unique challenges specific to PSSfCUP development. As Avison et al. (1999) stated, the complexity and distinctiveness of organisations stem from the individuals within them, who possess unique qualities separate from data and processes. People have diverse and conflicting goals, perspectives, and attitudes. They also transform over time. Therefore, systems analysts must acknowledge the fundamental human elements of organisations.

This research located the tool development process in an organisational setting that targeted the aforementioned challenges with the goal to study the power dynamic between different actors within the project. The article thus aims to contribute to the studies of UCD and answer the research question: How does a UCD approach perform during the development of a PSSfCUP? To answer the research question, three sub-questions were proposed:

- What is the role of the tool developers, users, and other actors during the tool development?
- How is the users' input considered?
- What challenges will be encountered during PSSfCUP development?

Background

GreenTwins Project and Virtual Green Planner

This article presents a case study about the digital tool development process in the GreenTwins Project. GreenTwins is a pilot project funded by the FinEst Centre for Smart Cities (FECSC). It aims to create and visualise a dynamic digital vegetation layer for the urban digital twins of Helsinki and Tallinn through user-friendly interfaces while also developing accessible physical and virtual spaces for digitally aided public participation and collaboration. One of the goals was to encourage consensus building or respectful debate, enabling the development and promotion of different planning alternatives by individuals.

To reach this goal, the project members developed two digital tools, as well as an algorithmic plant library and a physical venue (see Figure 1). Virtual Green Planner (VGP) is one of the digital tools that has been developed. VGP is a Unity game-engine-based application for co-planning urban and green areas in a three-dimensional (3D) environment. Its primary goal is to provide a user-friendly open-source planning and analysis tool for creating alternative plans by active citizens. It aims to enable the quick conceptualisation and draft of

plans and their analysis, facilitating CUP. As a PSSfCUP, VGP was not used in the official planning process but dedicated to citizens' self-organising participation. Its original idea was to create what-if scenarios (Klosterman, 1999) and share them through other media (e.g., social media and the physical space developed in GreenTwins) in an agonistic pluralism manner (Pløger, 2004) so that consensus was not forced. It aimed to provide the public with the power of a better argument or a better discourse strategy (Pløger, 2004). By the end of the GreenTwins project in May 2023, VGP had features including zoning, placing and deleting buildings, placing and removing vegetation, shadow analysis, sea flooding analysis, and vegetation growth simulation. Figure 2 shows the VGP user interface. The development of VGP is ongoing.

Figure 1: The products developed in the GreenTwins project to support CUP (Nummi et al., 2022).

Figure 2: VGP user interface.

Organisational settings

Figure 3 shows the organisational setting of GreenTwins, explaining the roles of different actors in the project. The project's organisational setting targeted the challenges of UCD methodologies (see Table 2). FECSC, which funded GreenTwins, was supported by European funding and state funding. It funded several pilot projects like GreenTwins through an open competition. Five teams of researchers, tool developers, technical staff, city representatives, and project managers were established within GreenTwins for different work packages. Team 1 was responsible for creating the algorithmic plant library; Team 2 was responsible for developing VGP; Team 3 was responsible for developing an urban environment simulation application. Team 1, 2, and 3 developed their products in parallel but also had frequent meetings to provide technical support to each other and ensure the interoperability of the developed products. Technical staff from partner cities participated in the meetings of these three teams to provide needed resources and technical support. Team 4 was responsible for the physical venue in Tallinn, Estonia. Team 5 worked closely with Teams 1, 2, and 4, bridging users and the developers through UR. Members of Team 5 included two researchers, one project manager, and a coordinator from a partner university. They organised user workshops, testing workshops, and tailored user questionnaires to the corresponding product. A member could participate in multiple teams at the same time. For example, the tool developer of VGP was the coordinator of Team 2 and participated in Teams 1, 3, and 5 meetings. In Team 5's meeting, the tool developer analysed the results of UR with Team 5 members and discussed the feasibility of the user requirements. At the same time, the coordinator of Team 5 was also a member of Team 2, and the project manager was a team member of both Team 2 and Team 5. The communication between these two teams was frequent and direct through the overlapping team members.

Figure 3: The organizational structure of GreenTwins.

VGP Development Process

VGP was developed by the developer and researchers in an iterative software development manner. In the early stages of the project, the funder requested the research and development to apply Agile development practices and engage various stakeholders, including end-users (Figure 4). VGP's development circle contained three steps: 1) user workshops/interviews, 2) evaluation and prioritisation, and 3) tool development. Participants, including researchers, planners, real estate developers, students, and active citizens, participated in the user workshops/interviews. They provided feedback and proposed user requirements. The feedback and user requirements were presented at the evaluation and prioritisation meeting, which most project members attended. The evaluation and prioritisation meeting decisions were then sent to the tool developer for further development. The newly developed version of VGP was presented and tested in the following user workshop, starting the next round of iterations.

Figure 4: The development process of VGP.

The iterative development approach aimed to integrate Agile processes, user engagement, and collaborative research and innovation work between the teams and representatives of the cities. The Agile approach was implemented as planned to some extent: the team members worked in close cooperation, met weekly, collaborated as the situation and needs arose, and joint review meetings were held every three weeks. However, user involvement did not occur as planned every three months but slightly less frequently. For example, for VGP, four user involvement events were organised during the project.

Methodology

The development process was studied through an action research approach (Avison et al., 1999). Researchers need to grasp the intricate and ambiguous nature of complex organisations (Avison et al., 1999). Neglecting to incorporate human factors might contribute to dissatisfaction with conventional information systems development methodologies, as they fail to address the realities of actual organisations. Therefore, we studied the organisational

structure within the project and power relations between different actors with interviews to understand the potential conflicts behind the scenes.

The lead author joined GreenTwins in 2022 when the project had been ongoing for over a year, and VGP had undergone several iterations. While actively participating in UR and tool development, the lead author observed the project from a third-person perspective. Observation covered meetings, communications between different actors, and decision-making in the project. Different versions of VGP were compared to identify the users' contributions. Archived meeting documents were reviewed. The lead author conducted semi-structured interviews with the developer responsible for VGP's development, one researcher, two project managers, one city representative, and one manager from the project funder. Questions were asked regarding the changes made to VGP and attitudes towards UR to gain insight into the decision-making process throughout the tool development (see Table 1). The interviews were recorded and transcribed.

Table 1: Interview questions

Question	Theme
1. What was your role in GreenTwins? What was your responsibility for this position?	
2. Who do you think was the most influential person in VGP's development? Could you please rank the involved partners?	
3. Do you think FECSC influences VGP's development? What was expected from VGP by FECSC?	Power dynamic
4. What do you think about the commercialisation plan of GreenTwins? Do you think it had any influence on VGP?	
5. What was the original goal of VGP? Was it changed? What is it now?	
6. Who was the target user of VGP, to your understanding?	Tool features
7. What should VGP look like in an ideal situation?	
8. Do you agree that VGP was developed using the process shown (an iteration process of VGP was presented to the interviewees)? Which phases did you participate in?	
9. What do you think about the users' engagement in the development process? Did any partners in the project require it?	Development process
10. How do you value the UR?	
11. Did you participate in the prioritisation meeting? Do you think your opinion matters in the prioritisation meeting? Who/what matters the most?	
12. In one of the UR workshops, participants required semantic data on buildings and vegetation in VGP, but this feature has not been implemented yet. How did you decide on this?	Power dynamic & Tool features & Development process
13. In one of the UR workshops, one active citizen suggested that the users should be able to get detailed information about the local environment (e.g., the history of trees and vegetation species). This suggestion was prioritised as level 3 (the least). How was this decision made?	

All materials were coded through an inductive coding approach. Interviewees' answers were compared with meeting documents. Interviewees' answers were categorised and summarised into a table for the authors to answer the research questions. Related data from different interviewees were put into the same row but in different columns in the table for comparison. Since each interviewee had multiple roles and responsibilities in the project, their roles were considered while analysing the answers, but they are anonymous in this article. It

should be noted that the developer and researcher interviewed are co-authors of this article. They also reviewed the interview data and other documents.

Results

What was the role of tool developers?

Interviewees were asked to rank the influential actors in VGP's development (see Figure 5). They all, including the developer himself, ranked the developer of VGP in the first place. This result was not a surprise since the idea of such a tool came from the developer's experience as an urban planning activist since 2012. The developer has engaged in a variety of urban and landscape planning projects across both the public and private sectors. He created a prototype to support an environmental NGO in visualising alternative plans for Central Pasila in Helsinki in 2013. That prototype was further developed at Aalto University for campus development as the predecessor of VGP in 2015-2016. During GreenTwins from 2021 to 2023, the developer worked simultaneously as a tool developer, PhD researcher, and activist in an NGO. Therefore, VGP was developed from both an activist and researcher perspective with a comprehensive understanding of the planning process. An interviewee who worked with the developer for several years explained: *'The user requirements were not from UR in GreenTwins but sensed by the developer intuitively in the past years. The developer himself was one of the target users, and he knew what features the target users wanted and how they should be done.'* The UR results also showed that the developer's knowledge about user needs was not a false consensus bias (Ross et al., 1977). The developer had noticed most of the requirements proposed by the users before the user workshops. However, the developer reserved the right not to implement some of the requirements he found irrelevant to VGP.

Figure 5: Influence ranking according to the interviewees.

Other tools' developers in Team 1 and Team 3 were ranked in the third tier by three interviewees and ranked in the second place by one interviewee. Since the digital tools and the physical environment developed in GreenTwins were supposed to work together, all tool developers worked closely to ensure their tools could be synchronised. They had regular meetings and helped each other with technical problems. An interviewee, who ranked Teams

1 and 3 in second place, argued that only people who can program and understand software development could have a constructive conversation with VGP's developer and, therefore, impact the tool development. He believed that others without technical knowledge failed to contribute. Other technical staff from the partner cities were ranked tier three or four together with the developers mentioned above by three interviewees, including VGP's developer. These technical staff did not directly work on VGP's development but provided necessary data and city models as the basis of VGP's 3D environment.

What was the role of users, and how was their input considered?

GreenTwins involved various potential user groups, including planners, real estate developers, active citizens, researchers, and planning students. As presented in Figure 5, all interviewees ranked the users in the fifth tier (last tier). During the development of VGP, the UR team mediated the users' inputs. They derived user stories based on the gathered user data. These user stories were subsequently evaluated during prioritisation meetings. Most interviewees acknowledged that the user engagement and research were well-conducted and significant. However, they also highlighted the insufficiency of integrating UR outcomes in a structured manner. The user data was utilised in research papers, but the project members were uncertain of its impact on the tool development. By the time of the research interview, UR in this project did not focus on usability testing but on identifying user needs and usability requirements. However, as per his previously mentioned target user role, the developer was aware of many user needs and usability requirements, and the UR only highlighted the importance of certain features.

Not all user groups were equally engaged in the development process. According to an interviewee, official planners and decision-makers were consulted more than active citizens or 'laymen' due to the active participation of partner cities. In contrast, active citizens, the original target users, *'were interested in tool development only if there was a real planning case'*, said the developer. He continued: *'When they find the planning case irrelevant, active citizens are less motivated than official planners who get paid for planning'*. This imbalance of user engagement led to an expansion of the use cases of VGP, initially designed for activists and citizens to use independently as a bottom-up public participation facilitation tool. After UR and development, VGP could support both administration-led participation processes and citizens' self-organised planning.

What were the roles of other actors?

The project funder of GreenTwins, FECSC, strongly emphasised public engagement, which was duly carried out. During interviews, some respondents noted that FECSC encouraged public engagement, making it a legitimate part of the project despite differing attitudes among the project members. Others expressed similar sentiments, stating that public engagement was essential in ensuring the project's eligibility for funding, as it was a mandatory

requirement in the application process. Yet, all interviewees believed the funder did not interfere with VGP's development (Figure 5). Although the participatory approach has been a critical factor in the project's development, systematic UR was not initially included in the project funding application. The funder prioritised a participatory element with adaptable implementation, allowing project members to develop the PSSfCUP according to their vision. UR was only introduced to the project when a researcher joined the team and was subsequently incorporated into the research and innovation plan.

Team 5, the UR team, was rated in the second tier (Figure 5). Team 5 members were perceived to work closely with tool developers, analysing data from UR and delivering the outcomes to the development team. They organised all the user workshops and the prioritisation meetings for the tools developed in GreenTwins. Additionally, they actively contributed to the design of the VGP user interface. Although Team 5 members conducted valuable UR, they felt the research outcomes were not adequately integrated into the tool.

In addition to Team 5 members, other project members were involved in the prioritisation meetings. During these meetings, all participants voted for the features they deemed essential for the users. Most interviewees who participated in these prioritisation sessions believed each participant had an equal voice in voting. However, one interviewee pointed out that since some researchers were responsible for drafting the user stories and requirements, they might have more influence in decision-making. Another interviewee observed that the prioritisation primarily relied on the researchers' perspectives, suggesting the need to link user groups to the specific requirements during the meetings to prioritise the primary user group accordingly.

What challenges did the PSSfCUP development encounter?

The challenges of applying UCD approaches identified by other scholars were eased to some extent through the project's organisational setting (see Table 2). Firstly, regarding the value and cultural differences, the funder and all project members, including the developer, supported UR. Secondly, for the different timelines, two dedicated teams were assigned to conduct Agile development and UCD approach parallelly. Thirdly, the funder replaced the typical role of a customer and supported user engagement but did not interfere with the tool development. Finally, to address the unclear responsibility, a dedicated team was established for UR and worked closely with tool developers.

While no one opposed UR within the project, there were varying attitudes towards it. These attitudes stemmed from constraints on time and resources, frequently cited by the interviewees as one of the main challenges encountered during tool development. Some project members, particularly those already heavily burdened with tool development, were frustrated with UR because it was not scheduled or resourced in the original tool development work packages.

Table 2: Organisational setting targeting UCD challenges and the results.

Challenges	Settings	Results
<p>Value and cultural differences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agile development emphasises testing functioning software and communication within the development team (Agile Alliance, 2001). UCD emphasises usability and communication with users (Larusdottir et al., 2017). Different attitudes towards UR (Ananjeva et al., 2020; Garcia et al., 2019). 	<p>The funder and all team members supported UR. The tool was developed by a motivated developer who is an experienced urban planning activist and urban planner. The developer participated in the UR closely with researchers and UX professionals.</p>	<p>Different attitudes towards UR existed but did not include standing against it.</p> <p>Both Agile and UCD approaches were applied, but both had limitations.</p>
<p>Different timelines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agile demands quick development and testing (Agile Alliance, 2001). UCD spends much time studying users before development (Al-Razgan et al., 2022). 	<p>Two teams proceeded in parallel with Agile development and UCD research. The tool concept was established years before the project and development. UR focused not on measuring usability but on understanding the users' needs and identifying usability problems.</p>	<p>User needs were gathered in two workshops, but the development process did not strictly follow the Agile development as planned.</p> <p>UR was conducted too late in the development process. The asynchrony between the tool developer and other project members hindered the realisation of users' needs. The developer needed more time and resources to follow the Agile approach and realise all feasible user requirements.</p>
<p>Customers and users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agile does not distinguish between customer and user (Martin et al., 2004). UCD requires direct user involvement (Gould & Lewis, 1985). 	<p>The project did not have a customer. A funder supported the project and the UCD approach and did not interfere with the tool's development. The developer himself was a target user, and the project funder emphasised the involvement of potential users, such as planners, active citizens, real estate developers, etc.</p>	<p>Users had more influence than the funder, but the developer had the power to decide whether the user requirements were feasible.</p> <p>The commercial plan did not include VGP, and its profitability had little impact on its development.</p>
<p>Unclear responsibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is often unclear who is responsible for the interaction between the development team and users (Gulliksen et al., 2003; Larusdottir et al., 2017). 	<p>A dedicated team (Team 5) was established for UR. Most of the project members discussed and prioritised user stories and requirements.</p>	<p>UR was collaboratively implemented with the development teams and successfully carried out. Team 5 frequently communicated user needs to the tool developer. UR results were used in research and articles, but not all were implemented in VGP.</p>

The lack of time and resources led to a gap between user requirements and the features in VGP. For example, semantic data for city models, such as detailed information on individual buildings, existing environments, and ongoing plans, were proposed by various user groups, but has not yet been incorporated. When questioned about the reason for that, several interviewees explained that semantic data was planned to be implemented since the project's inception. However, there was not enough time for the developer to go through thousands of buildings and vegetation in the city model, as the data sets provided by the partner cities were not ready to use. Although the city model was provided in the developer's desired format, its attributes were in custom fields. Without comprehensive transcription, the developer could not link the semantic data and the city model in the Unity environment.

The lack of time was not a result of the UCD approaches but stemmed from the project's nature. Firstly, the developer was solely responsible for VGP's programming while keeping multiple roles. Developing a PSS while conducting research and writing academic articles was challenging. One interviewee suggested that researchers should not be tasked with programming and that dedicated programmers or software development companies should be hired to meet user requirements. Secondly, the project planning did not accurately estimate the demand for tool developers. Another interviewee acknowledged this as a mistake and noted that more developers and resources were needed to address user needs identified in the UR. *'Universities are not the most attractive employers for programmers who can find better resources in the industry'*, she stated. The project's research nature limited resources available for additional programmer employment.

The second challenge was the power of the tool developer. All interviewees agreed that the developer had the power to control the direction of VGP's development and decide what to implement in the tool. They also agreed that the developer deserved this power not only because he was the only programmer for it but also because they all acknowledged that it was 'his product'. VGP was derived from the passion of the developer instead of the potential of profiting like some other commercial applications. In this case, the tool developer valued UR due to his role as an activist and doctoral student researching public participation in planning. As a result, users' opinions were considered in the development process, although some requirements were rejected based on the feasibility or suitability according to the developer.

'Feasibility' and 'suitability' were mentioned several times by the developer during the interview while explaining the rejected requirements. This implied a misunderstanding of VGP and mismatched expectations from it by the users and even the project members. In contrast to the developer's long-time engagement with VGP, the project members and the potential users started to be involved in the development only in 2021. The different timelines between them explained their asynchrony. For the developer, the tool development has been through the fuzzy front end and has reached the prototype phase (Sanders & Stappers, 2008). He expected incremental contributions aligned with his idea from the participants, while some

project members expected an open idea collection through user research. The developer said, *'In the prioritisation meeting, people voted for what they wanted but did not know the whole picture.'* *'There were some weird choices,'* he pointed out. For example, one rejected user requirement was the feature of placing small items like benches and trashcans in the 3D environment. This requirement was mentioned by many workshop participants several times but was not implemented. Two interviewees explained that a too-detailed design feature was unimportant for VGP since the tool was for larger-scale planning instead of detailed planning. The developer had the power to decide not to implement such a feature in VGP. No organisational power-balancing mechanism was seen in the project except for the time and resource constraints and the developer's preference for UCD approaches.

The third challenge was the commercialisation of the developed tools. GreenTwins has both research and commercialisation goals. FECSC received external funding to fund pilot projects (Figure 3). Although it was a non-profit organisation, its funding sources required it to operate sustainably. To achieve this, FECSC aimed to commercialise its pilot projects and generate profits that would be used for daily operations, research, and new pilot projects. GreenTwins' commercialisation plan targeted the project as a whole rather than individual tools, allowing VGP to remain open-source and non-profit. One interviewee confirmed that the funder emphasised the project's commercial plan while at the same time stressing the importance of keeping VGP open-source after the developer insisted on it during the funding application. Different strategies were employed for other tools in the project to balance commercialisation and open-source characteristics. Two interviewees expressed concern that an open-source product would be difficult to commercialise, particularly given that the target users were active citizens who were unlikely to pay for the tool. Another two interviewees believed that VGP was not affected by the commercialisation plan. Similar to the challenge of the overpowered tool developer, no balancing mechanism was seen to constrain the project funder from demanding profitability. The non-commercial nature of VGP was secured only because the developer insisted on it being open-source, and the funder agreed.

Discussion

This article investigated the application of UCD approaches in developing PSSfCUP through a case study. It highlighted the critical role of **tool developers**, the indirect inputs from **users**, the **UR team's** mediator role, and the **project funder's** fundamental role in the development process. The insights into the power dynamics between these actors revealed a systemic problem between them.

This research exposed the potential risk of overpowered **tool developers**. We argue that tool developers' covert power (Clegg, 1989) comes along with the nature of the development of PSSfCUP. If the target users (e.g., individuals of the public, active citizens) are not ideal customers, the PSSfCUP is not easily commercialised or profitable. Therefore, such PSSfCUP

is not likely to be developed by commercial companies with adequate resources but initiated by motivated, independent developers. Spontaneous developers with unlimited power may overlook the users' needs even if they favour UCD approaches. By determining the feasibility and suitability of user requirements, the developers can influence decisions, prevent decisions from being made, and shape preferences and decisions (Lukes, 2004). If a project wants to ensure user influence in the development process by implementing UCD approaches, it requires examining power dynamics and impact pathways more closely (Reed & Rudman, 2023).

VGP's developer believed he was one of the target users and could somewhat represent the **users**. However, choosing and defining user groups is crucial in the UCD approach (Benyon et al., 2005; Nielsen, 1993). This research also faced challenges at this step. The researchers identified a range of user groups at the start of the project through stakeholder mapping (Nummi et al., 2022). As the project aimed to develop tools for the broader public, it was challenging to identify the primary user groups due to the diverse needs of potential users. Although the original target users were active citizens, which the tool developer aimed to support, more user groups were included during the tool development process. Not to mention that the group of 'active citizens' consisted of individuals with multiple roles and various expertise.

The result of users being ranked as the least influential during VGP's development by all interviewees aligns with the depiction of users' role in UCD: a subject of study and informants (Friedrich, 2013; Sanders & Stappers, 2008). Friedrich (2013) argued that users do not necessarily have contact with each other and are led by professional tool developers. Moreover, they are involved in the process only when the professionals request their input. Given the challenge of users not articulating their requirements easily (Hyysalo, 2010; Sanders & Dandavate, 1999), developers must comprehend users' capabilities, characteristics, goals, and practices. Therefore, UR is essential to the development of a PSSfCUP. However, by doing so, the users' voices in this project were mediated by researchers through UR. In the studied case, Team 5, the **UR team**, was closer to the development than the users. There was a risk that this team, who held more power than others, could influence users' engagement towards supporting a specific epistemology, method, or predetermined outcome, as Few (2001) described as 'containment of participation'. Although researchers in Team 5 and the project funder sought user engagement to ensure that the developer heard user voices, there was still a need to discuss the possibility of unintentional misrepresentation (Colvin et al., 2016).

The **funder** played a fundamental role in VGP's development by encouraging user engagement and giving researchers and the developer freedom to design the user involvement methods and software development process. A well-designed development process that considers power dynamics can benefit all stakeholders (Reed & Rudman, 2023). If VGP were designed entirely by researchers based on UR and developed by professional programmers,

the power of tool developers would be balanced. However, developing a PSSfCUP is time-and-resource-consuming, so the funding source is critical. While individual citizens are not likely to pay for a PSSfCUP, non-profitable funding is needed to design such a tool for the public. If the funder expected a profit from the product, a user group with more potential to pay would be targeted. Paying for the planning software could pose problems, especially if the price is high. This may limit access to only wealthy citizens or those who deem it worth the investment. Those who cannot or are unwilling to pay for the tool will have fewer opportunities to participate.

As Rydin (2000) suggested, reducing the cost could encourage more successful participation, and we argue further that the development of completely free and open-source PSSfCUP would be ideal in terms of opportunities for participation. Keeping VGP open-source ensures that everyone can develop and modify it. Open-source software, such as QGIS¹ and Blender², are maintained by their communities through voluntary work despite receiving sponsorships and donations. Both software were also used to support VGP development. PSSfCUP, like VGP, could follow the same open-source model. However, one challenge with PSSfCUP is that they may have a smaller user base than software providing production value. Maintaining its continuity can be difficult when the software community is not large enough. A significant portion of open-source software consists of academic research tools, but research grants for software development rarely allocate funds for long-term support and maintenance (Heron et al., 2013). Moreover, only a small proportion of individuals involved in open-source development are employed and receive financial compensation from the larger companies supporting open-source initiatives (Feller et al., 2005). There is also a risk that citizens without programming skills would be excluded from developing the tool. The continuously evolving nature of open-source software requires updating documentation to reflect every change in the user experience (Heron et al., 2013). Developers frequently overestimate the computer skills of novice users (Knight & Jefsoutine, 2022), so even when documentation is well-maintained, it is often presented in a way that is not easily accessible to beginners.

When programmers autonomously develop a PSSfCUP, it is questionable whether they will use UCD approaches. The knowledge gap about user needs between digital tool developers and target users (Nielsen, 2008) still exists. Even if those voluntary developers are both users and developers, like VGP's developer, whether their collective self-study about user needs will help depict a more precise user profile needs to be studied. A new partnership between tool developers, users, researchers, and funding sources is needed to foster an open-source PSSfCUP for the public.

Some limitations exist in this research. Firstly, we did not interview the potential users who attended the user workshops. We could have benefited from their feedback on how the

¹ <https://www.qgis.org/community/involve/>

² <https://www.blender.org/get-involved/>

improvements of VGP satisfy them. Secondly, VGP was not tested in a real-world planning case. Without implementing the tool in a real case, either in an agonistic (Pløger, 2004) or communicative (Healey, 1992) manner, we could not see the tool's impact on public participation and, therefore, failed to verify the development process's influence on public participation.

Conclusion

CUP is an arena of power where various stakeholder groups influence the planning process through various participatory approaches. Unlike the traditional participatory approaches that could be modified and adapted to specific planning cases by the users, PSS are pre-made by tool developers. In the digital era, due to the development and usage of digital participatory tools, the stakeholders are forced to hand over their power to tool developers to some extent.

The challenges of implementing UCD approaches in the Agile development process (Al-Razgan et al., 2022; Gulliksen et al., 2003; Larusdottir et al., 2017; Silva da Silva et al., 2011) were eased by the organisational setting in the studied project. Yet, new challenges were revealed. The findings showed that the developer was overpowered in the tool development but faced limitations of time and resources. The users' inputs were restricted due to their misunderstanding of the tool and the developer's authoritative decisions, although UR was conducted frequently and carried out clear user stories and requirements. The users relied on the UR team to deliver their requirements to the tool developer.

This study highlighted the power dynamics between tool developers, users, UR teams, and funders in the PPSfCUP development. It is essential to consider these dynamics and diverse voices when designing stakeholder engagement strategies (Reed & Rudman, 2023) with UCD approaches. While Larusdottir et al. (2017) suggested empowering UR experts to ensure usefulness to users, we recommend establishing a healthy relationship between all four parties that balances their power and results in the creation of open-source PPSfCUP for the public.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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